

UPQC BASED POWER QUALITY IMPROVEMENT OF SOLAR PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS USING ANFIS AND MFA

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Abstract:

The ability of energy to reach consumer devices is determined by the quality of the power that was used to create it. Using a Unified Power Quality Conditioner (UPQC) improves the power quality on feeders in distribution system. The Unified Power Quality Conditioner is the most effective customized power equipment available in the market. An UPQC system with a three-phase bus that is fed by PV is modeled and tested. Sagging is caused by heavy loads, whereas swelling is caused by light loads. Solar arrays fed by UPQC are becoming increasingly popular as a means of reducing the severity of these power quality issues. The ANFIS-PSO based MPPT method has no extra sensor requirement for measurement of irradiance and temperature variables. The employed methodology delivers remarkable driving control to enhance PV potential extraction. The Classical maximum power point tracking (MPPT) techniques, developed for uniform solar radiation on PV arrays such as P&O algorithm sometimes, are unable to discriminate between local and global maximum power points. Therefore, this research under partial shading condition (PSC) is aimed for enhancing the efficiency of the PV system by using modernistic techniques such as ANFIS-Particle Swarm Optimization (ANFIS-PSO), and ANFIS BASED Modified Firefly Algorithm (ANFIS- MFA). The main function of each algorithm is to find the optimal duty cycle for the DC-DC converter in order to increase the output power and efficiency. The P&O algorithm shows larger convergence time with high oscillation as compared with the other three algorithms which showed success in finding and tracking the GMPP, especially the last algorithm (MFA), as it was characterized by its speed, efficiency and convergence in finding the GMPP compared to the previous algorithms. The ripple in MFA in steady-state conditions is lower than P&O, PSO, and FA methods.

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Introduction

UPQC is a custom power device (CPD) utilized for eliminating the PQ problems such as harmonics [1] unbalance, sag and swell and phase-angle jump due to the extensive usage of electronically switched devices and non-linear load [2,3]. This CPD comprises of both shunt and series converters coupled through a common DCLink voltage and deals with harmonics in load current and also imperfections in source voltage [4]. The shunt converter can eliminate current harmonics and unbalances from the nonlinear load so that

perfect sinusoidal current flows through the power network, however series converter can compensate voltage sag/swell, voltage unbalance, voltage distortion and phase-angle jump present on the source side, so that perfect voltage regulation is maintained across the load [5]. Therefore, UPQC draws the consideration of power engineers to create active and adaptable solutions to PQ issues, which leads to the development of novel topologies and advanced control systems for UPQC. Control system plays an important part in the overall performance of a

The photovoltaic panels harness the solar energy from the sun. The utilization and functionality of the UPQC can be increased by integrating with solar energy [12]. The photovoltaic system is modelled mathematically using MATLAB Simulink. The PV panel output is DC voltage. The output of the PV panel is boosted and fed to the common DC link capacitor. The MPPT controller like ANFIS BASED PSO is used to track the maximum power from the solar panels, and compare MFA MPPT [13].

II. UPQC power circuit configuration

The power circuit configuration of UPQC is shown in Fig. 2. It comprises of series converter and shunt converter. The series converter is a three phase PWM voltage source inverter, which mitigates voltage sag, swell, voltage distortion and voltage unbalance existing in the supply voltage. Subsequently, the LC filter consists of inductor L_{sef} and capacitor C_{ef} connected in output of series converter to prevent the flow of switching ripples

[14]. Similarly, the transformers are connected at the output of the LC filter to provide isolation between series converter and the power line and also prevent the DC-link capacitor from being short circuited due to the operation of various switches. The power circuit of shunt converter consists of a three phase PWM voltage source inverter, which is connected through an interfacing inductor L_{shf} to provide isolation between the shunt converter and power line [15]. The purpose of shunt converter is to restrain the load current harmonics and to control the DC-link voltage. However, insulated gate bipolar transistors (IGBTs) with anti-parallel diodes are used as PWM voltage source inverter and a 3-phase diode-bridge rectifier employed with resistive RL as well as inductive LL are used as a nonlinear load [16].

Fig. 2. Power Circuit Configuration for UPQC

III. Solar Cell

Sun based cells are intended to change over (something like a part of) accessible light into electrical energy, as their name recommends. They achieve this without depending on synthetic cycles or moving parts.

Characteristics of Solar Cells

The sun based cell, which is for the most part built of PV wafers, changes over sun oriented illumination's light energy straightforwardly into voltage and flow for load, and conveys power without the utilization of an electrolytic impact [17]. The electric energy is acquired from the PN interface of semiconductor straightforwardly; accordingly, the sun based cell is otherwise called PV cell .The same circuit of sun based cell as displayed in Fig 3.

Fig.3. Equivalent circuit of PV array

The latest source, photovoltaic cell current is addressed by I_{ph} , the nonlinear obstruction of the p-n intersection is addressed by R_j , and the natural shunt and series protections are addressed by R_{sh} and R_s , separately. Typically, the worth of R_{sh} is very high, though the worth of R_s is somewhat low. Therefore, the two of them may be disregarded to improve on the investigation. PV modules are comprised of PV cells that are assembled in bigger groupings [18].

The $I_{ph} = [I_{scr} + K_i(T - T_r)] \frac{S}{100}$ equal mix to shape PV clusters. The numerical model used to work on the PV exhibit is addressed by the condition.

$$I = n_p I_{ph} - n_p I_{rs} \left[e^{\left(\frac{q}{kTA} \cdot \frac{V}{n_s} \right)} - 1 \right]$$

Where I addresses the PV cluster yield current, V addresses the PV exhibit yield voltage, n_s addresses the quantity of series cells, n_p addresses the quantity of equal cells, q addresses the charge of an electron, k addresses the Boltzman steady constant, addresses the p-n

IV. Hybrid ANFIS–PSO Based MPPT Controller

The training and updation of ANFIS specifications are a challenging task for the designers nowadays. Compared to the gradient techniques, the PSO provides simpler and rapid updation convergence velocity [20]. Moreover, the PSO does not require initial parameter calculation and nor there is requirement of a learning rate. Fig. 4 depicts the architecture of the ANFIS controller and comprises antecedent and conclusions as a major component with five total layers [21].

intersection ideality factor, T addresses the cell temperature, and I_{rs} addresses the cell invert immersion current. The sun powered cell's uniqueness from the best p-n intersection character is dictated by factor A chooses the deviation of sun oriented cell from the best p-n intersection attributes. It's worth reaches from one to five. The photograph current I_{ph} relies upon the sunlight based irradiance and cell temperature as below

Where I_{scr} is the cell short circuit current at reference temperature and radiation, K_i is the short circuit current temperature coefficient and S is the solar irradiance in mW/cm^2 . The Simulink model of PV array is shown in Fig. 4. The model includes three subsystems. One subsystem to model PV module and two more subsystems to model I_{ph} and I_{rs} [19].

Fig.4. Architecture of an ANFIS Controller

The mathematical equations associated with multilayer feedforward network are as follows:

$$W_j = \mu_{P_j}(x) * \mu_{Q_j}(y), \quad \bar{W}_j = \frac{W_j}{W_1 + W_2}, \quad j = 1, 2.$$

$K_1, K_2,$ and K can be expressed as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} K_1 &= A_1x + B_1y + R_1z, & K_2 &= A_2x + B_2y + R_2z \\ K &= \frac{W_1K_1 + W_2K_2}{W_1 + W_2} = \bar{W}_1K_1 + \bar{W}_2K_2 \end{aligned} \right\}$$

The membership function (bell-shaped) lies between 0 and 1 and is evaluated mathematically as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mu_{P_j}(x) &= \frac{1}{1 + [((x-r_j)/p_j)^2]^{b_j-3}} \\ \mu_{P_j}(x) &= \exp \left[- \left[\left(\frac{x-r_j}{p_j} \right)^2 \right]^{b_j} \right] \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Fig. 5. Membership Functions Input Framework

INFERENCE FUZZY DECISION

E	NB	NM	NS	Z	PS	PM	PB
NB	Z	PB	Z	Z	NS	PB	PB
NM	PS	Z	NS	Z	NS	Z	NM
NS	NB	Z	PB	PS	PS	PS	PS
Z	Z	PS	NM	Z	PS	Z	NS
PS	Z	NB	PB	NS	Z	Z	PS
PM	NS	NS	PS	Z	NS	PS	PB
PB	PS	PS	Z	NB	Z	PM	NB

Unlike traditional MPPT controllers, this control has peak maximum power tracking, fast dynamicity, the rapid velocity of convergence, and simpler contraption. Fuzzification, inference engine, and defuzzification are the premier process blocks of this algorithm. The MATLAB/Simulink model of an ANFIS– PSO methodology in the presence of an input parameter (PV voltage/current) yields duty ratio as pulse width modulation (PWM) generated signal [22] [23]. The detailed flowchart structure of an ANFIS–PSO-based MPPT control is described in Fig. 6. An advanced hybrid ANFIS technique gathers the fuzzy data with trained learning rules for proper adjustment of membership values before the error has been minimized to the merest amount. Whenever membership parameters are adapted, the learned system is equipped to work as a hybrid MPPT controller

Fig. 6. Flowchart Structure of an ANFIS-PSO based MPPT Control

V. Modified Firefly Algorithm

In general, the population size for PSO and FA is constant. A larger population is beneficial to the global search process, but it increases tracking time. On the other hand, a low population decreases the tracking time of research, but might a trip to the local MPP instead of the global MPP. The modified firefly algorithm (MFA) is proposed, Where the main point behind this algorithm is an adaptation of population size, so, the coefficients of the algorithm (α , β_0) are updated in each iteration, to obtain poise between convergence speed and the tracking efficiency. α and β_0 are defined as follows:

$$\alpha = \alpha_{max} + (\alpha_{min} - \alpha_{max}) \frac{iter}{Max,iter}$$

$$\beta_0 = \beta_{0,max} + (\beta_{0,min} - \beta_{0,max}) \frac{iter}{Max,iter}$$

Where iter is the iteration number and Max,iter presents the maximum number of iterations. As can be seen in above Eq, the value of the parameter α is large at the first iteration, then, it is lowered in the next iterations for accelerating the convergence and decreasing the tracking time this lead to lower the chance of trapping in the local optimums. Furthermore, when β_0 reduced at each iteration, the convergence speed raises.

The steps of MFA algorithm to MPPT

- 1-Set the initial parameter of MFA such as randomization parameter and attractiveness.
- 2- Suppose population size.
- 3- Simulate the Simulink module.
- 4- extract the output power that's specified the brightness of the firefly.
- 5- Update the duty cycle value that's represented by the position of firefly depending on the optimization technique that's applied.
- 6- Check the restrictions and run the best solution

VI. SIMULATION RESULTS

Case1: Hybrid ANFIS-PSO based MPPT Controller

Fig.7.Behavior of grid and inverter.(a) Grid behavior at unity power factor. (b) Inverter pursuance

Fig.8.Grid voltage & current waveforms (a) Low to high insolation level (b) High to low insolation level

low insolation level

Fig. 9. Grid synchronization. (a) Inverter voltage, grid voltage and inverter current under steady-state conditions insolation current under (b) Grid and inverter under dynamic operating conditions

Fig.10. Performance of hybrid MPPT under changing solar steady-state conditions

Case 2: Hybrid ANFIS-MFA based MPPT Controller with UPQC

Fig. 11. Simulation of Hybrid ANFIS-MFA based MPPT Controller with UPQC

Fig. 12. Grid Voltage and Grid Current waveforms

Fig. 13. Shunt Inverter Voltage and Shunt Inverter Current

Fig. 14. Load Real Power and Reactive Power Waveforms

Fig. 15. Load Voltage and Current

Fig. 16. Power send by Grid

Fig. 17. Power send by Inverter

Fig. 18. Power send by Grid

Fig.19. Battery State of Charge

Fig. 20. Battery Management – Battery Voltage, Battery Current

Fig.21.Simulation result of shunt converter, (a) shunt converter compensation waveforms during steady state condition and (b)shunt converter compensation waveforms during transient state condition.

Fig. 22.Simulation result of shunt and series converter (a) shunt converter compensation waveform during load unbalance condition and (b)series converter compensation waveform during voltage distortion condition.

Fig. 23. Simulation results of unbalanced supply voltage and phase angle jump (a) supply voltage unbalance
 Compensation waveform (b) Phase angle jump and variation compensation during sag condition

Fig.24. PV responses at Unity Power Factor

Fig. 25. (a) Voltage Swell V_{dc}

(b) Voltage Sag V_{dc}

(c) Voltage distortion V_{dc}

(d) Unbalanced nonlinear V_{dc}

(e) Load change V_{dc} comp1

(f) Load change V_{dc} comp

Fig.25 (a) Voltage swell

(b) Voltage swell

Fig. 26. (a) Voltage distortion

(b) Voltage distortion V_{dc}

(c) Unbalanced nonlinear load

(d) Unbalanced voltage

vdc

Fig.27 (a) Source Voltage Distortion

(b) Source voltage

V_{dc}

(c) Load Constant V_{dc}

(d) Load constant current

(e) Load change V_{dc}

(f) Load change current

Fig. 28.Total Harmonic Distortion Analysis on Source side as well as Load side (a) Source Voltage THD

(b) Source Current THD

(c) Load Voltage THD

(d) Load current THD

VII. Conclusion :

This paper emphasizes on design and performance analysis of photovoltaic array integrated unified power quality conditioner (PV-UPQC) and presents the idea of power quality enhancement along with the green energy transfer to the grid. PV array is integrated with UPQC by using maximum power point tracking (MPPT) circuit (boost converter and MPPT algorithm). PV-UPQC is dealing with power quality issues such as unbalanced current, harmonics, reactive power, dip and swell in the supply voltage. It will also transfer active power from the PV array to the load and/or grid depending upon solar radiation.

In this paper, a novel fixed frequency FSMPWM based control strategy is presented for UPQC. The proposed control methodology is responsible for fast and accurate tracking of the reference signal along with providing fixed switching frequency during power system perturbations and also eliminates the inherent chattering drawback of sliding mode control. The P&O algorithm is not efficient in finding the global maximum power point of the PV system, especially in the second scenario. Also the P&O algorithm shows larger convergence time with high oscillation as compared with the other three algorithms which showed success in finding and tracking the GMPP, especially the last algorithm (MFA), as it was characterized by its speed, efficiency and convergence in finding the GMPP compared to the previous algorithms. The MFA method proved to be the best MPPT tracking method compared to other three methods in all cases, Therefore, it successfully compensates several PQ problems such as current harmonics, load unbalance, voltage sag/swell, voltage unbalance, voltage distortion and phase-angle jump existing in the power distribution network and makes UPQC robust in comparison to the conventional SMC method during power system perturbations.

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